

THE ROLE OF ETHICS IN RESEARCH METHODOLOGY IN QUALITATIVE RESEARCH**Asha Rawat**Research Scholar, Khun Khun Ji Girls Degree college,
University Of Lucknow**ABSTRACT**

Ethical questions arise at every stage of the research process from initial design through fieldwork and analysis of research findings. This paper consider principles and level of research ethics and how these apply in qualitative research and data analysis stages. Researchers should refer to some ethical guidelines to ensure they have adhered to the principles of good research practices. This paper focus on the ethical perspective in a given situation that we generally need to follow in qualitative research when collecting and analyzing data. These include maintaining scientific integrity, upholding human rights and dignity, ensuring social responsibility, building trust in researcher and the participants and protecting their safety.

Keywords

-Ethics, Scientific integrity, Human Right and Dignity

INTRODUCTION

Ethics are the principle and guidelines that's helps us upholds the things we value. It is a set of norms that make the research work more authentic. Research ethics is a commitment to ensuring that the pursuit of knowledge remains trustworthy and beneficial for participants and society. Embracing research ethics means prioritizing the well-being rights and rights of study participants and maintaining accuracy in data collection. Ethics revolve around the responsibilities of researchers towards their participants, their audience, their society, and their academic communities. Basically, the term 'ethics' refers to moral principles of guiding conduct, which are held by a group or even by professional. It is associated with the discipline like philosophy and theology.

Ethics is often defined as a system of moral principles, which standard and concept defined systematized and recommended concept of right and wrong behavior. Ethics is related at least to an extent also. Therefore it is agreed that subject moral, social, political, and cultural back forms the shape of Ethics in the relevant environment. Ethics in research involve the application of fundamental ethical principles to planning, conducting and publishing of research. It is also ensures scientific integrity, protects participants and maintain public trust.

RESEARCH ETHICS IN RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

One of the important part in research methodology is research ethics, it refers to some of the genres that researcher follow to protect the rights in developing research strategies and guidelines that insure integrity, honesty and fairness in the research process. Ethical standard ensures that it enhances the possibilities of credibility and valid result from the research and building a trusted relationship between the study participants and investigators.

IMPORTANCE OF ETHICS IN RESEARCH

Research ethics are integral to all forms of research. They help protect participants' rights, ensure that the research is valid and accurate, and help minimize any risk of harm during the process. Ethics in research are important to ensure the credibility and integrity of the research process while protecting the rights and welfare of participants. It also ensuring social responsibility and building trust in research and institutions and with appropriate ethical standard Protecting Participants safety.

The benefits of observing ethics in research studies are as follows:

1. It helps in promoting the aims of research, such as bringing out the truth and avoidance of errors.
2. It promotes the values that are essential to collaborative work, such as trust, accountability, mutual respect and fairness.
3. It hold the researcher accountable to the public and society.

IJETRM

International Journal of Engineering Technology Research & Management

Published By:

<https://www.ijetrm.com/>

4. It helps in building public support for research, which in return can help in getting participants who take part in the research willingly.

PRINCIPLE OF RESEARCH ETHICS

1. **Honesty**- honesty in reporting data, results, method and procedures, and publication status.
2. **Objectivity**- objectivity to avoid bias in experimental design, data analysis, interpretation and peer review.
3. **Integrity**- integrity, acting with sincerity for consistency of thought and action.
4. **Carefulness**- carefulness to avoid careless errors and negligence and proper documentation of all aspects.
5. **Openness**- openness in sharing data, result, idea, tools, and resources and openness to criticism and new ideas.
6. **Respect**- respect for intellectual property right, such as patent, copyright and other forms of intellectual property.
7. **Confidentiality**- confidentiality in context of communications, personal record and privacy issues.
8. **Responsible publication**- Responsible publication, with the aim to serve the society. Avoiding wasteful and duplicative publications.
9. **Responsible Monitoring**- In terms of guiding research students.
10. **Respect for Others**- Respect for colleagues translate to extending fair treatment to colleagues.
11. **Social Responsibility**- Means to serve the society and different stakeholder.
12. **Non-discrimination**- against colleagues or student on the basis of sex, race, or factor that are not related to their scientific competence and integrity.
13. **Competence**- enhancing competence for own professional advancement or lifelong learning and taking steps to promote competence in science as a whole.
14. **Legality**- Ensuring legality of the whole process by obeying relevant laws, i.e., institutional and government policies.
15. **Animal Care**- Animal care through proper experimental design.

Ethical issues in research

Ethical issues arise when the conduct of the study conflicts with moral principles, leading to potential harm or exploitation of participants. Addressing these issues it is important to maintain the credibility and trustworthiness of research and ensure that it benefits society without causing harm.

1. **Voluntary participation**- Participants are free to opt out of the research, experiments or study at any given stage.
2. **Informed Consent**- Participants are made aware of the purpose, benefits, risk and funding before agreeing or declining to join.
3. **Anonymity**- where researcher are not aware of the identities of the participants therefore personal data can not be collected.
4. **Confidentiality**- where researcher know the participants identities and must keep all personal information confidential.
5. **Potential Harm**- Physical, Social, psychological and legal harm must be kept as minimal as possible to ensure maximum safety of participants.

Some of the key terms used in the context of ethical issues concerning researchers are as follows-

1. **Fabricating Behaviour**- Creation of spurious data by researcher, their recording and drawing inferences.
2. **Falsification**- it manipulate the research material, equipment and processes or change data or results such that the research is not accurately represented in the research records.
3. **Plagiarism**- it is the act of appropriating somebody else's ideas, thoughts, pictures, theories, words or stories and presenting as your own.

CONCLUSION

The researcher should follow the research ethics so that their research should be unique. The researcher needs to see that it should be free from plagiarism and that the idea is not copied. Research Ethics is important while doing any kind of research. The importance of ethics in research cannot be neglected as it makes the research more believable. Ethics need to be followed very religiously in any type of research.

REFERENCES

- 1- American psychological association (APA) / 2017 ethical principle of psychologist and code of conduct. Retrieved from <http://www.apa.org/ethics/code/ethics code-2017>.
- 2- Bhattacharya, Asmita(2020), The Role of professional ethics in teacher education page no.-30-33 Naveen shodh sanasar (An international refereed / peer review research journal) ISSN 2320-8767, E-ISSN 2394.

IJETRM

International Journal of Engineering Technology Research & Management

Published By:

<https://www.ijetrm.com/>

- 3- Dooly M. Moore E & Vallejo, C(2017). E. qualitative approach to research on plurilingual education(pp.351-362) research publishing net <http://doi.org/10.14705/rpnet.2017>
- 4- Gujjar.B.Nilesh(2015) 'Ethical Consideration in Research , International journal for Research in Education, Vol 2, issue: 7 (IJRE) ISSN 2320- 0091X
- 5- Mirza Hadjeri Bellalem Fouzi(2023), Ethical Consideration in Qualitative Research Summary Guidelines for Novice Social Science Researchar ,'Social Studies and research Journal ISSN 2352-9555 V(11) No 1. 2023 PP441-449
- 6- Marcelle Cacciattolo(2015), 'Ethical Consideration in Research' The Praxis of English language teaching and Learning, (PEET) (pp 61-79)
Doi: 10.1007/ 978-94-6300-112-0-4
 - www.sciencedirect.com
 - [www. Egyankosh.ac.in](http://www.Egyankosh.ac.in)>uni
 - [www. Slideshare.net](http://www.Slideshare.net)>slideshare